

Software Risks for Critical Infrastructure towards 2040: Round 1 Report

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INTRODUCTION

This document reports on the first round of a Delphi Study, addressing the following question:

What effect may change in the nature and use of software systems between now and 2040 have on the potential for major incidents related to UK Critical National Infrastructure (CNI), especially as related to the Civil Nuclear, Communications, Energy and Health sectors?

The sections explore the context for CNI as described by participants; trends they identified; the resulting new and enhanced risks; then some possible mitigation approaches suggested in the discussions. Lastly, a diagram shows the relationships between trends, risks and mitigation approaches. Descriptions of the participants and the method can be found in the appendix.

CNI CONTEXT

As introductory context, the participants provided several insights into the nature of Critical National Infrastructure software:

1. **Commercial drivers:** CNI are operated by public and private sector organizations; industry's commercial, innovative visions will influence CNI technology strategies and their implementation.
2. **Longevity of software:** As infrastructure, much of the software is long lived: up to many decades. It is hard to preserve developer knowledge over those timeframes.
3. **Definition of CNI:** Definitions of CNI vary considerably, from 'sufficient to recover from nuclear attack' (UK 1950s), to 'anything politically sensitive' (USA currently). The current UK definition is, roughly, services in 13 sectors where threats include *major* loss of life, casualties, economic or social impacts; or impact on national security or state functioning.

4. **Only respond to regulation:** Organisations in highly regulated sectors, such as nuclear, energy and health, tend not to be proactive, but wait for regulation to define their response to risk.

GENERAL TRENDS

The interviewees identified the following trends related to CNI, more important ones first:

1. **IoT and other next generation technologies:** By 2040 there will be extensive use of Internet of Things (IoT) technology such as smart sensors and edge sensors, as well as Digital Twin and Cloud based technologies.
2. **System complexity and interconnectivity:** By 2040, increased complexity and interconnectivity will make CNI systems more difficult to design, understand and manage.
3. **Increase in digitisation:** Towards 2040, most systems will become software-controlled, to increase efficiencies, decrease costs, for data accessibility and to free up physical space.
4. **Decentralisation of services:** Towards 2040, digitisation will enable decentralisation of the operation and delivery of CNI services. Remote communications, wireless and radio technologies will allow the dispersal of functions like electricity generation, including nuclear in the form of Small Nuclear Reactors.
5. **Increased end-user dependency on technology:** 2040 will see increased reliance for consumers on software and machines to carry out and plan activities.
6. **System operators working through software, not directly:** By 2040 humans' participation in CNI processes will increasingly be through complex software systems rather than directly with hardware or simple software controls .
7. **Changing geopolitical context:** Towards 2040, two major trends will affect CNI software:
 - a. Segregation of countries into separate blocs with differing values and standards.
 - b. Climate change and green energy movements driving digitisation and automation to mitigate harms.
8. **New CNI:** Towards 2040, increasing digitisation will lead to aspects of the internet themselves becoming critical infrastructure.
9. **Artificial intelligence:** Towards 2040, advances in Artificial Intelligence (AI) will open doors to increased and improved automation, situational awareness, data sharing and interpretation, as well the development of more efficient, and effective systems.
10. **Quantum computing:** By 2040, quantum computing will be starting to support solutions to a set of optimisation and cryptographic problems for a few international companies and nation states.
11. **Off-the-shelf hardware and software:** Towards 2040, CNI systems will increasingly be made from off-the-shelf hardware and software components.

RISKS IDENTIFIED

The main focus of this study is on new and changed possible risks. Our participants identified the following:

1. **Poor response to accidents or attacks:** Towards 2040, we shall see increasing failure to identify and respond to adverse events due to:
 - a. Poor human response due to lack of training or trust in bad quality data or obscure algorithms,
 - b. Additional malicious activity, or
 - c. Glitches in AI-based situational awareness and guidance.
2. **Attacks via humans:** Towards 2040, cyberattacks will increasingly involve humans as well as machines, both insider threats and attackers focusing on human vulnerabilities such as taking advantage of weak passwords or manipulating people into taking inappropriate actions, even when the software works as specified.
3. **Sociotechnical problems:** By 2040, digitisation and the increased complexity of systems—including the operators and responses of users—will lead to increasing accidents despite all the participants working in good faith (as happened in the Three Mile Island and Chernobyl incidents).
4. **Cascading problems:** Towards 2040, increased interconnectivity will mean that minor problems, or failures in non-essential elements, will sometimes escalate and affect wider, vital aspects of a system. The complexity of systems will make it difficult to identify such vulnerabilities.
5. **Failure from failed electricity, telecommunications or internet:** By 2040, much of CNI will not be able to function without these. For example, a widespread loss of electricity supply would prevent delivery of all of transport, communications, health services, food, and other critical services.
6. **Unprotected repair or diagnostic technology:** Towards 2040, the increasing use of off-the-shelf software and hardware components used in CNI will introduce vulnerabilities, especially where the components are designed without security concerns in mind. Examples would be replacement sensors with additional internet features, or 'digital twins' insufficiently protected.
7. **Democratisation of attacker technology:** By 2040, advanced technology will be widely available to malicious parties and lay people who, intentionally or accidentally, will cause damage on systems and infrastructure. E.g. AI enhanced attacks.
8. **Software and hardware supply chain problems:** 2040 will see increasing issues with the provision of software and equipment, system maintenance and related services. There will be an increasing disconnect between technology users and developers, and between procurement and technical specialists, as well as conflicts with the commercial interests of suppliers.
9. **Common mode failures:** Towards 2040, geographically dispersed systems will increasingly have monoculture technologies (systems, components and vendors) for portions of their

operations, which will share the same vulnerabilities. These will allow mass replicated attacks or lead to other mass failures.

10. **Magnification of problems through social media:** By 2040, issues of misinformation and disinformation will escalate relatively small problems into mass panics, which then cause further failures (this was a feature of the [Colonial pipeline incident](#))
11. **Electromagnetic storm:** There is a reasonable chance, by 2040, that an electromagnetic pulse, from the sun or a distant nuclear bomb, will destroy many vital components of modern infrastructure. This may involve disabling power grids, communication systems and computer networks with catastrophic economic and social consequences.
12. **Radio hacks:** By 2040, connections that are currently wired—especially in nuclear—will be replaced with radio connections, leading to successful cyberattacks using radio interception.
13. **OT attacks:** By 2040, many aspects of Operational Technology (OT) will be integrated with Information Technology (IT) and IoT (Internet of Things, or sensor technology) which will be used by cyber attackers to destroy or disable electromechanical systems.
14. **Commercial dangers:** By 2040, increasingly, supplier commercial considerations will exacerbate the damage done by cyberattacks: for example unwillingness to repair, to stock components, or to supply services when the charging system is down ([Colonial pipeline](#)).
15. **Unpredictable AI:** Towards 2040, as AI is increasingly introduced, the occasional inconsistency and unreliability of AI outputs will lead to damaging accidents—whether directly in control systems, or by causing incorrect operator actions.
16. **Poisoning of AI:** Towards 2040, cyberattackers will tamper with the datasets used to train AI models, causing incidents directly, or allowing ‘loopholes’ to allow the attackers access to vulnerable systems.
17. **AI-based phishing, whaling and similar attacks:** Towards 2040, generative AI will be widely used in fraudulent communication, by video, email and voice, leading to damaging incidents, the installation of malware, and other issues.
18. **AI identifying vulnerabilities in software:** Towards 2040, cyberattackers will increasingly use AI to find new vulnerabilities in standard software components or in systems accessible on the web, allowing them access to secure systems.
19. **Quantum-enabled breaking of encryption:** In the 2040 timeframe, nation states and rich corporations may be able to ‘crack’ the encryption algorithms currently in use, potentially allowing them control of sensitive installations.

RISK MITIGATION

The experts recommended the following strategies now to address these risks.

1. **Systems resilience approach:** Designing and organising to provide resilience (in addition to cybersecurity), such as incident planning, redundancy in provision, and gradual degradation.

2. **Secure systems by design:** Incorporating systems security, privacy and safety analysis—including human interaction analysis—from the earliest stages of design in creating and modifying software systems.
3. **Research into Sociotechnical approaches:** Research into the non-technological/human aspects of CNI system security.
4. **Improved risk management:** Investment in risk management: organisations identifying what can go wrong, why and how likely it is; and taking steps to mitigate each risk.
5. **AI and new technology for incident management:** AI can help with incident planning and risk management, with training exercises; and with situational awareness.
6. **AI for incident prediction and detection:** The combination of smart sensors, ‘digital twins’ and AI can spot trends and anomalies that human-only teams might miss.
7. **Systems testing including red teaming:** Testing and verification for entire systems, including human operators.
8. **Tracking existing attacks and failures:** Legislation and systems to ensure anonymised data sharing of all commercial cyberattacks and serious software failures related to CNI.
9. **Systems diversity:** Regulation and guidance to promote software (and hardware) diversity, to create resilience against vulnerabilities.
10. **Education of stakeholders:** Training about the dangers of AI-enhanced ‘phishing’, and more basically, about what digitalisation means for their roles.
11. **Training of professionals:** Integrating security and resilience into software education; improved training about software contracts.
12. **Diplomacy around cyber threats:** Threat of military response to serious cyberattacks; imprisonment of hackers captured while travelling.
13. **Research into sociotechnical errors:** Academic research into why human errors happen, and ways to mitigate social engineering.
14. **Legislation and government support for resilience:** To address the ‘commercial dangers’ problems.
15. **Business as Usual cybersecurity research and practice:** Activities that are currently being strongly promoted and carried out.

Figure 1: Relationships between Trends, Risks and Mitigation Approaches

SUMMARY

Figure 1 summarises the relationships between the trends, risks and mitigation approaches outlined in the previous sections, as identified by the interviewees. The arrows show which risks arise from each trend, and which approaches were identified as addressing each risk.

Figure 2: Delphi Study Method

APPENDIX: METHOD

In this project we used a Delphi-style study to leverage expert advice in a relatively short time. Figure 2 shows an overview of this approach. The recruited experts give their best predictions by answering open questions. The researchers then use qualitative analysis techniques to identify themes in those predictions and synthesize a summary from the opinions. Feedback is provided by participants and the summary is adjusted accordingly; this iterative process may continue for further rounds.

In this study, we devised a set of open-ended questions around the research question, aiming to generate roughly an hour of discussion. We asked experts to propose 'game-changer' technologies, their impact in their field and to suggest how combinations of these technologies might play together. We then asked them to identify large risks, provide examples of how these risks might come about and suggest ways to mitigate them. To conclude, we asked experts to comment on the impact on CNI of five relevant forecasts around software futures that we identified in a previous project.

We piloted the questions in interviews with two people working in similar areas to the topic, to establish timing, comprehensibility, and completeness. Two researchers separately analysed the pilot interview transcripts and identified problems in timing and the question sets effectiveness to answer the research question. We amended the set of questions accordingly.

At the same time, we recruited professionals whose roles involved anticipating trends in software, cybersecurity, and CNI. The process of recruiting and interviewing specialists for the first round took two months. As the topic is a sensitive one, we used a referral approach, asking academic and industry colleagues of the lead authors for referrals. By 'snowballing' further referrals from each expert who agreed to be interviewed, we recruited 22 specialists from academia, industry and government. We carried out one-hour interviews with each specialist, recording and automatically transcribing each discussion.

Two researchers then separately ‘open coded’ each interview transcript. Both coders then met to discuss their themes and to synthesize their results to address the research question. The research results are presented in this document.

In the analysis, we were aware that there is a wide knowledge and understanding of the several technical trends (AI, quantum computing, etc.) and of a range of obvious cyber risks that may derive from them. Indeed, there is already funding and research into mitigating some of these risks. In the interest of providing research value, in this study we looked for wider risks and possible new research approaches to address them.

APPENDIX: RESEARCH PARTICIPANTS.

Table 1 is an anonymised list of our participants. P1, P2 from the pilot study are omitted. The third column estimates their professional experience in years, including postgraduate research; the fourth their current country. P8, P15, P21, P22 and P24 identify as female; the others as male. Columns ‘Nuclear’ through ‘Military’ indicate specific areas of CNI expertise for each participant (colours distinguish columns). Column ‘CNI’ indicates where a participant has expertise related to CNI cybersecurity in general; and the rightmost column indicates where they have professional experience with regulation or government policy on CNI topics.

Table 1: Interviewees

ID	Description	Exp. (yrs)	Country	Nuclear	Energy	Telecoms	Health	Transport	Internet	Military	CNI	Reg/Policy
P3	Academic specializing in cybersecurity and resilience of networked systems.	26	UK	█								█
P4	Government scientist specializing in security of software systems.	26	UK							█		█
P5	Government scientist specializing in security of nuclear systems.	37	USA	█								█
P6	Academic leading major group covering cyber security and advanced computing	33	Austria			█					█	█
P7	Academic leading group researching future digital resilience	24	UK		█						█	
P8	Human factors and cybersecurity expert working in the rail industry	20	UK					█				
P9	Industry program director working on digital twins	27	UK		█			█				
P10	Academic leading (different) research project into future CNI risks	26	UK								█	█
P11	Independent OT cyber security consultant, working with industry and government	40	UK									
P12	Academic leading cyber futures research institute	9	USA						█			█
P13	Academic, from industry, specializing in future health informatics	28	UK				█					
P14	Academic specializing in government policy related to future cybersecurity risks	40	UK								█	█
P15	Consultant specializing in emergency management	10.	UK	█				█				
P16	Academic specializing in cybercrime relating to emerging technology	30.	Canada								█	█
P17	CEO of industry consultancy specialising in OT cybersecurity	15.	UK					█			█	
P18	Consultant in engineering and regulation to industry and government	40	UK	█	█							█
P19	Academic expert at networking and AI resilience	46.	UK			█					█	
P20	Academic specialising in international security, especially cyber warfare.	13.	UK							█	█	
P21	Research analyst specialising in future cybertechnology and national security	5	UK				█					█
P22	Industry Consultant expert at future study and software	55	UK									█
P23	Senior academic specialising in cybersecurity, law and future technologies	40.	USA						█		█	█
P24	Researcher studying future resilience	5	UK					█			█	